

Rechecking Recheck Requests in Continuous Integration: An Empirical Study of the OpenStack

Appendix

This document is an online appendix for “Rechecking Recheck Requests in Continuous Integration: An Empirical Study of the OpenStack”

Section 3 MF-1:

Fig. MF1.1. Hierarchical clustering of features based on Spearman's rank correlation. The line shows $\rho = 0.7$

Section 3 MF-4:

Fig. MF4.1. Dotplot showing the Spearman multiple ρ^2 of each feature and the likelihood of successful recheck.

Section 4 RQ1:

- N/A handling strategies

Table RQ1.1. Performance metrics for N/A handling strategies

	AUROC	Brier Score	AUPRC
Change N/A values to 0	0.751	0.182	0.590
Change N/A values to 1	0.730	0.189	0.531
Remove N/A values	0.736	0.191	0.604

- Comparing traditional machine learning methods to statistical logistic regression results

Table RQ1.2. Performance metrics for traditional ML using time-based 10-fold cross-validation and statistical logistic regression using 1000 bootstrap iterations.

	AUROC	Brier Score	AUPRC
Statistical logistic regression bootstrap	0.736	0.191	0.604
Logistic regression	0.733	0.192	0.572
Random Forest	0.731	0.190	0.583
XGBoost	0.725	0.193	0.581
SVM	0.729	0.194	0.562

Section 4 RQ2:

- Analysis of one bot and multiple-bot rechecks

To understand the impact of the “bots success ratio” on recheck outcomes, we compared rechecks involving one bot to those with multiple bots. Of the total 314,947 rechecks, 208,925 involve a single-bot, which is twice as many as those with multiple bots (106,652). Rechecks with multiple bots are 1.5 times more likely to fail, with a prediction accuracy of 0.65 for single-bot rechecks and 0.82 for those with multiple bots. This higher accuracy suggests that multiple-bot rechecks are more predictable, likely due to their higher failure rate. The data highlights the key role of bots involved and their past performance in recheck outcome prediction.

Fig. RQ2.1. Dotplot showing the Spearman multiple ρ^2 of each feature and the likelihood of successful recheck.

- Additional analysis of “when” feature family.

Despite the overall insignificance of many features within the “when” family, the significance of the “queued hour” feature ensures that the family contributes significantly to the model fit. Figure RQ2.1 shows that rechecks mostly occur in the afternoon (i.e., 1 PM to 3 PM) with a peak at 2 PM (34,717). Rechecks occur least often at night (i.e., 10 PM to 5 AM) with 4 AM being the minimum (15,399).

- Response curves for each feature

Fig. RQ2.2. Response curves

Fig. RQ2.3. Response curves (Cont.)

Fig. RQ2.4. Response curves (Cont.)

- Nomogram with all features

Fig. RQ2.5. Nomogram with full set of features

- Additional Observation. The “diff avg failure” feature value becomes a deciding factor when values are set to extreme.

Figure RQ2.5. shows that even though the “diff avg failure” feature is ranked third by importance, it becomes a deciding factor when values are set to extreme. As the “diff avg failure” feature value increases, the nomogram shows a nonlinear relationship, with a larger gap between values above 0. The difference in predicted probability between 0.1 and 0.9 is 36 points (i.e., from 72 to 108), which makes up 22.5% of the total points. This shows that small changes in feature values can result in substantial differences in the predicted outcome.

Section 5 analysis:

- Jobs success ratio response curves for different window sizes

Fig 5.1. Response curves

Fig 5.2. Response curves (Cont.)

- The model performance across the studied window sizes:

Table 5.1. Model performance per different window sizes.

Window size	AUROC	AUROC Optimism	Brier Score	Brier Score Optimism	AUPRC	AUPRC Optimism	Obs.	% Success Rate
1 day	0.74243	0.00016	0.19442	-0.00005	0.64046	0.00032	145,379	37.6
1 week	0.73806	0.00011	0.19330	-0.00004	0.62359	0.00020	225,124	36.4
2 weeks	0.73818	0.00011	0.19232	-0.00004	0.62242	0.00017	241,444	36.0
1 month	0.74077	0.00005	0.19050	-0.00001	0.61904	0.00014	253,916	35.5
3 months	0.74187	0.00001	0.18929	-0.00001	0.61346	0.00006	263,477	35.0
6 months	0.74147	0.00007	0.18872	-0.00002	0.60825	0.00016	268,653	34.6
1 year	0.74062	0.00001	0.18832	-0.00001	0.60482	0.00004	272,789	34.3
All time	0.73893	0.00002	0.18826	0.00000	0.60128	0.00012	274,797	34.1